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APPROACH TO DIAGNOSTICS AND TESTING OF FIBER OPTIC COMMUNICATION LINES

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Annotation: The article considers an approach to the development of new principles of diagnostics and testing of fiber-optic communication lines. The development of new principles of diagnostics and testing of fiber optic communication lines is becoming increasingly important in practice and does not lose its relevance. The problems that arise during the actual operation of fiber optic communication lines require not only technological, but also fundamental research. A decisive contribution to the solution of these problems can be expected from the use of computer and mathematical modeling methods, which, in turn, can also contribute to the development of new approaches in these areas of science and technology.

Keywords: fiber optic communication lines, intellectual informatively-measuring systems, intellectual potential, diagnostic facilities, optoelectronic devices, diagnostic parameters

ПОДХОД К ДИАГНОСТИКЕ И ТЕСТИРОВАНИЮ ВОЛОКОННО-ОПТИЧЕСКИХ ЛИНИЙ СВЯЗИ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается подход к разработке новых принципов диагностики и тестирования волоконно-оптических линий связи. Разработка новых принципов диагностики и тестирования волоконно-оптических линий связи приобретает все большую практическую значимость и не теряет своей актуальности. Проблемы, возникающие при реальной эксплуатации волоконно-оптических линий связи, требуют проведения не только технологических, но и фундаментальных исследований. Решающий вклад в решение этих проблем можно ожидать от применения методов компьютерного и математического моделирования, что, в свою очередь, может способствовать и развитию новых подходов в этих областях науки и технологии.

Ключевые слова: волоконно-оптические линии связи, интеллектуальные информационно-измерительные системы, интеллектуальный потенциал, средства диагностики, оптико-электронные устройства, параметры диагностики волоконно-оптические линии связи

At present, there is a powerful development of technologies for fiber optic transmission of information. The formation of fiber optic communication technologies puts forward more and more new problems that are predominantly systemic in nature or are associated with specific specifics of operating conditions. Optical fiber and cable are a fairly new industrial product, and their performance and properties are being actively studied. The development of new principles of diagnostics and testing of fiber optic communication lines is becoming increasingly important in practice and does not lose its relevance. The problems that arise during the actual operation of fiber optic communication lines require not only technological, but also fundamental research. A decisive contribution to the solution of these problems can be expected from the use of computer and mathematical modeling methods, which, in turn, can also contribute to the development of new approaches in these areas of science and technology.

Creation of the informatively-measuring systems (IMS) and introduction to their composition of the digital computing engineering and devices of memory brought development over of methods of

algorithmation and programming towards the sharp increasing of intellectual potential of IMS.

Presently largely demand rose to the intellectual informatively-measuring systems (IIMS) able to execute such functions as: to carry out the grounded choice of algorithm in concrete situations, on the requirements to procedure to determine aims and terms of measuring, take into account the imposed limitations on a priori information.

Presence of possibility of choice of algorithm of measuring and adaptive varying of his parameters depending on present of a priori and current information, apparatuses and temporal limitations criterion of quality of results of measuring and terms of conducting of measuring, is basic dignity of intellectual informatively-measuring systems (IIMS).

In this case it is necessary to attribute to the intellectual functions of the indicated system: processes of measuring, control, diagnosing and recognition, designing, methodological, services and general systems intellectual functions [1, 2].

At the decision of intricate complex problems – systematic upgrading products and perfection of the control system by production, application of IIMS is required. It allows promoting authenticity of information about quality of initial materials, technological processes state parameters of the prepared products.

Perspective of application of devices of optoelectronics in the checking and management systems is related to their large informative capacity carrying capacity, ideal galvanic upshot of entrance from an output, wide nomenclature of the transformed electric and other sizes, possibility to constructions of both primary facilities of collection of information and devices of reflection, by the breadth of peak and frequency range of measuring of entrances sizes, simplicity of docking with computer.

Therefore maintenance of the capable of working state of the optoelectronic systems is one of basic functional tasks of IIMS, the decision of which will allow creating the effective measuring systems.

Correct choice of method of diagnosing of the concrete system or device and, in particular, diagnostic parameters (DP), is an actual task. To avoid errors at the choice of DP it is necessary to carry out complex quantitative estimation of aggregate of parameters and on its basis to choose the best DP.

The first requirement is executed by minimization of nomenclature of estimation indexes and initial information necessary for their calculation; comforts of determination of these indexes and calculation of the generalized index of quality of DP. The requirements of the second point are determined by the choice of substantial fixed and reference-equivalent indexes.

The account of ponder ability of indexes can be attained by a selection approximately equivalent their nomenclature and introduction at a necessity gravimetric coefficients. It should be noted also, that a method must provide unity of approach to the choice of different on purpose of DP and to take into account their specific. Complex estimation on the aggregate of indexes of choice of DP of fiber optic cables is resulted in Table. 1.

Table 1 – Basic rationed technical-spare indexes of DP

Index	Calculation formula	Index	Calculation formula
1. Universality a) on the number of the checked up structural parameters of one OE device of diagnosing	$VI=IF/I_0=\sum Q_i/I_0$ (1) where IF, I_0 is the middle actually checked up and common number of structural parameters of the checked device up; Q_i is probability of determination of I parameter	5. Number of performers	$KI=1/KF$ (7) where KF is minimum number of performers
b) on the number of checked different up OE devices of diagnosing	$Y_0=nF/n_M$ (2) where nF, n_M is the actual and maximal number of the checked devices up.	6. Technological	$T_n=1/Z$ (8) where Z is necessity for verification number of types of repair-technological equipment and other facilities
c) on the number of the engulfed types of fiber optic	$Y_M=N_{OE}/N$ (3)	7. Cost	$C=C_M/CF$ (9) where C_M , CF is the actual and minimum cost of

Index	Calculation formula	Index	Calculation formula
devices (OE) from the examined aggregate (N)			diagnostic mean
2. Informing	$J = I_p / I_0 = \sum Q_{pi} / I_0 \quad (4)$ where I_p is middle number of parameters recognizable in case of occurring of disrepairs; Q_{pi} is probability of recognition of disrepair on an I parameter	8. Compatibility	$C_n = P \quad (10)$ where P is probability of implementation of verification of performers
3. Exactness	$E = EFEN \quad (5)$ where EF , EN is actual and normative exactness of determination of structural parameter	9. Generalized index of quality of method (parameter)	$K_0 = \sum v_i K_i = \left(2E + \sum_1^v K_i \right)$ K_i are private indexes on nn.1.2.4.8, v_i is specific gravity of I - index (11)
4. Control possibility	$\Sigma = \Sigma_M / \Sigma F \quad (6)$ where Σ_M , ΣF is actual and minimum duration of verification		

Note. In formulas (2), (6), (9) the maximal and minimum values of constituents get out from the aggregate of the examined methods.

The analysis of requirements shows to DP, that the applied methods and facilities of diagnosing must provide:

- most complete estimation of the technical state of the checked object up (Y_n);
- possibility of verification of different optoelectronic devices of the diagnosed system (Y_0) and most aggregate of the systems (Y_c);
- recognition of concrete disrepairs on leaving of DP for the assumed limits (J);
- required exactness of diagnosing (E);

- minimum his duration (τ);
- implementation of diagnosing by one performer (KN);
- conducting of diagnosing with the use of the least of auxiliary equipment, adaptations, instruments (T_n);
- possibility of the use of the most economic diagnostic facilities (C);
- most sociological compatibility (C_n).

Indexes of Y_i and J , essentially, characterize a necessity in additional facilities (devices and adaptations) for diagnosing of the optoelectronic systems and their component parts, E is exactness of determination of structural parameter by value of diagnostic, τ it is operativeness of verification, KN is necessity in labors resources, T_n are comforts of verification, C – simplicity and cheapness of diagnostic mean, C_n is attitude of performers toward verification and in this connection probability of its implementation. All estimated (private) indexes are represented in the rationed kind with the range of change 0.1. Indexes 1, 2, 4, ..., 8 approximately equivalent, and index it is suggested to adopt 3 (exactness) with the doubled coefficient of ponder ability [3-5]. The data analysis of tabl.1 shows that to expect all indexes and to find generalized very not difficultly. It is confirmed, in particular, with the results of the use of this method at the choice of different DP [6, 7].

In Table 2 DP and methods of quality control of the made elements included in the structure of fiber optic communication lines/cables, got with the use of the offered method, and summary information of results of analysis of DP is resulted in Table 3.

Table 2 – Descriptions of DP and methods of quality control of fiber optic cables

Method of verification	DP or high-quality sign	Description of parameter										
		Yn	Y0	YM	J	E	τ	KN	Tn	C	Cn	K0
1. Power	1.1. Resistance	0,01	0,5	1,0	0,01	0,11	0,95	1,0	0,5	1,0	1,0	0,56
	1.2. Conductivity	0,01	0,5	1,0	0,05	0,32	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	0,66

Method of verification	DP or high-quality sign	Description of parameter										
		Yn	Y0	YM	J	E	τ	KN	Tn	C	Cn	K0
2. Optical	2.1. Spectral range	0,20	0,5	1,0	0,20	0,84	0,33	1,0	0,33	0,04	0,5	0,53
3. Analytical	3.1. Fiber-optic cables	0,8	0,5	1,0	0,28	0,74	0,30	1,0	0,25	1,0	0,7	0,66
	3.2. Devices of fiber optic cables	0,8	0,5	1,0	0,34	0,84	0,25	1,0	0,20	0,1	0,6	0,59
4. Physical	4.1. Fiber optic mobile elements	0,8	1,0	1,0	0,20	0,95	0,10	0,5	0,15	0,01	0,5	0,56
	4.2. Fiber optic microprocessors	0,8	1,0	1,0	0,20	0,74	0,15	1,0	0,25	1,0	0,8	0,66
	4.3. Measuring charts of fiber optic devices	0,8	1,0	1,0	0,5	0,9	0,3	1,0	0,5	0,1	0,0	0,7
	4.4. Sources of feed of fiber optic cables /devices	0,8	1,0	1,0	0,60	1,0	0,20	0,5	0,15	0,1	0,4	0,61
5. Physical and chemical	5.1. Complete aggregate of indexes of fiber optic communication lines	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	0,02	0,25	0,10	0,01	0,2	0,60

Table 3 – Priority of DP and methods of quality control of fiber optic communication lines

Number of parameter (accordant tabl.2)	Total value	Priority group
4.3	0,73	I
4.2.	0,69	II
1.2; 3.1	0,66	
4.4	0,61	
5.1	0,60	
3.2	0,59	III
1.1; 4.1	0,56	
2.1	0,53	

Similar calculations are executed on the nomenclature of DP for verification of acoustic-optical, magnet-optical, fiber-optical transformers of the checking and management by technological parameters systems [8]. The results of these calculations on the whole confirm sufficient simplicity and efficiency of method of choice of DP and allow recommending it for practical application.

Bibliography

- [1] Bystrov D. Approach of Digital Devices Diagnostic on the Basis of Fuzzy Logic/Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Networking, Information Systems & Security, 2021, Marocco. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3454127.3456570>.
- [2] Michael Beck, Ethernet in First Mile, McGraw-Hill, New York, 2006.
- [3] W. Goralsky, SONET/SDH, McGraw-Hill, 2002.
- [4] Kazi K. Optical Networking Standards, Springer, New York, 2006.
- [5] Keiser G. FTTX Concepts and Applications, John Wiley & Sons Hoboken, NJ, 2006.
- [6] Listvin A.V. Reflectometry of optical fibers / A. V. Listvin, V.N. Listvin. – M.: LESARart, 2015. 208 c.
- [7] Portnov E. Optical communication cables. Designs and characteristics / E. Portnov. – M.: Hot line-Telecom, 2012. 232 p.

[8] Ubaidulaev, R.R. Fiber-optic networks / R.R. Ubaidulaev. – М: Technosphere, 2013. 237 p.

Список литературы

[1] Быстров Д. Подход к диагностике цифровых устройств на основе нечеткой логики/Материалы 4-й Международной конференции по сетям, информационным системам и безопасности, Марокко, 2021 г. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3454127.3456570>.

[2] Майкл Бек, Ethernet на первой миле, McGraw-Hill, Нью-Йорк, 2006 г.

[3] Горальский В. SONET/SDH, McGraw-Hill, 2002.

[4] К. Кази, Стандарты оптических сетей, Springer, Нью-Йорк, 2006 г.

[5] Г. Кайзер, Концепции и приложения FTTH, John Wiley & Sons Hoboken, Нью-Джерси, 2006 г.

[6] Листвин А.В. Рефлектометрия оптических волокон/ А.В. Листвин, В.Н. Листвин. – М.: ЛЕСАРарт, 2015. 208 с

[7] Портнов Э. Оптические кабели связи. Конструкции и характеристики/ Э. Портнов. – М.: Горячая линия-Телеком, 2012. 232 с.

[8] Убайдулаев Р. Р. Волоконно-оптические сети/ Р.Р. Убайдулаев. – М: Техносфера, 2013. 237 с.

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